
Living Labs for citizen-centric energy transition - learning from oPEN Lab

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Abstract: The aim of the oPEN Lab project is to revitalize urban areas across Europe, leading the transition to Positive Energy Neighbourhoods (PENs) by demonstrating the feasibility of promising technologies in an integrated, participatory, and neighbourhood-based approach.

Three oPEN Living Labs in Genk (BE), Pamplona (ES) and Tartu (EE) are set up as open innovation hotspots for testing combinations of close-to-market ready technologies and services and study their performance as a unique operating system. Based on the eliciting needs from citizens, new innovators are also involved in the Living Labs. Within the project, ENoLL is responsible for the capacity building and mentoring concerning the Living lab approach. In our presentation we will focus on the best LL-practices developed, (e.g., community-based artworks, open houses, renovation-as-a-service), but also focus on the challenges concerning stakeholder engagement and barriers for Living Lab growth.

Keywords: Living Labs; energy transition; neighbourhood-based approach; community-based arts, barriers to growth

1. The oPEN Lab project

oPEN lab¹ is an EU-funded project (Horizon 2020, grant agreement n°101037080) aiming to upgrade existing buildings and district facilities in specific neighbourhoods in the cities of Tartu, Pamplona and Genk to fully operational Positive Energy Neighbourhoods (PENs) and manage them as oPEN Living Labs.

According to European Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan Action 3.2, supported by the “Positive Energy Districts and Neighbourhoods for Sustainable Urban Development” programme², a Positive Energy Neighbourhood (PEN) is understood to be an energy-efficient and energy-flexible urban area or group of connected buildings, which produces net-zero greenhouse gas emissions and actively manages an annual local or regional surplus of renewable energy³.

oPEN Lab tests and demonstrates promising technologies in an integrated approach combining the sustainable design tailored to the local context, the industrial renovation workflow as well as the generation of renewable energy combined with storage systems. To achieve its goals, the project engages and involves the local neighbourhoods' communities in the three cities to create a vision for their PENs by using citizen-centric participatory approaches within the oPEN Living Labs.

Figure 1 oPEN Lab project main website visual

2. Three oPEN Living Labs

¹ <https://openlab-project.eu/>

² <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/ped/>

³ Komminos, N. (2022). Net Zero Energy districts: Connected intelligence for carbon-neutral cities. *Land*, 11(2), 210.

Within the oPEN Lab project, three Living Labs¹ in the cities of Pamplona (Spain), Genk (Belgium) and Tartu (Estonia) are set-up with the aim of transforming neighbourhoods into PENs. The three Living Labs driven by a consortium of local stakeholders including the actors of the quadruple helix (government, academia, private sector and society) are working on neighbourhoods of different typologies, spatial and social contexts.

oPEN Living Lab Pamplona

The oPEN Living Lab in Pamplona implements one of the first operational Positive Energy Neighbourhoods in Spain. The main area of the Living Lab is the northern district of Rochapea, a working-class neighbourhood dating back to the 1940s. Within the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona deep energy renovations of a former industrial site (IWER) and two apartment blocks of the San Pedro housing group are carried out.

Figure 2 Rochapea area of the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona

Achieving an active commitment of citizens and other local social agents, crucial in becoming a PEN, included using the Living Lab Mapping Canvas² to design the Living Lab activities in line with the Living Lab Integrative process³, creating a Living Lab strategy plan and strategic roadmap. Currently, already two Renewable Energy Communities (REC) are in place (Arrotxa-e, and NovoRochapea). Arrotxa-e arose after a

¹ <https://openlab-project.eu/living-labs/>

² <https://enoll.org/methods/living-lab-mapping-canvas/>

³ <https://energylivinglab.com/toolbox/>

participative process lead by Pamplona City Council, and including training on Energy Communities (energy management, legal aspects etc). It was formally established in June 2023 and the City Council keeps providing them advice and support through the PEN Office. Next to this, the oPEN Living Lab is an essential part of the citywide Agenda Urbana Pamplona 2030¹.

oPEN Living Lab Genk

The oPEN Living Lab in Genk is located in the suburban residential neighbourhood called "Waterschei". This area consists of two different areas: a more recent social housing district from the 1990s called "Nieuw Texas", and a former miner's district from the 1920s. This combination provides a unique possibility to bring together a total of 33 dwellings (including 27 social housing units) within the Living Lab for large-scale and real-life demonstrations of promising technologies (e.g. the collective energy box²), process and social innovation via a collective renovation concept towards the creation of Positive Energy Neighbourhood. Moreover, a collective energy building in the middle of Nieuw Texas is being co-created together with the residents and local communities in the neighbourhood.

Figure 3 Waterschei area of the oPEN Living Lab Genk

The oPEN Living Lab Genk has adopted a diversified approach to engage with citizens, targeting vulnerable groups as well, including information sessions, interactive

¹ <https://www.pamplona.es/estrategia-2030-agenda-urbana-de-pamplona>

² <https://lito.be/en/products/litobox-17>

workshops, individual home visits, informal gatherings and both written and digital communication channels. Moreover, the oPEN Living Lab Genk got integrated into a broader Open Thor Living Lab¹ in the same region to secure the continuity of oPEN Living Lab beyond the end date of the oPEN Lab project.

oPEN Living Lab Tartu

Originally, the oPEN Living Lab Tartu was planned to focus on the city district of Annelinn, a socio-demographic diverse and densely populated neighbourhood built during the Soviet occupation in the 1970s and 1980s. It is characterised by typical high-raised panel houses with limited public spaces and prevailing parking spaces around the buildings. The oPEN Lab Tartu had a very ambitious goal to become a positive role model for Estonia by increasing the quality of life in the Annelinn neighbourhood. However, the current economic situation with higher renovation costs, inflation, increased interest rates and financial uncertainty caused a major setback since interested housing associations were no longer able to fund the renovation works and disengaged from the initiative. As a result, the oPEN Living Lab Tartu partners needed to explore alternatives and found a new neighbourhood in the district of Veeriku that allows the envisioned implementation and roll-out of social and technical innovations.

Figure 4 Shift of neighbourhood in oPEN Living Lab Tartu from Annelinn (arrow A) to Veeriku (arrow B)

Despite this major setback mostly caused by external factors, the oPEN Living Lab Tartu used many of the lessons learned from the stakeholder engagement activities in the

¹ <https://www.openthor.be/en>

Annelinn neighbourhood forward to the new area. It allowed them to create a co-creation and co-design programme for the residents of Veeriku, including a cost calculation tool¹, multiple information events, a dreaming workshop and multiple study visits, together with an updated survey focused on social aspects.

3. The mentoring programme, knowledge transfer framework and capacity building handbook

Within the project, an extensive work has been undertaken by the Energy Living Lab from the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO)² and the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)³ to develop a Capacity Building Handbook and Mentoring report⁴, including one to one interviews and follow up meetings with each oPEN Living Lab, documentation of examples and tools from oPEN lab, use case interviews and presentations with energy living labs across the ENoLL Network as well as the presentation of Living Lab theory and how it has been practically implemented in each of the three oPEN Living Labs. Mentoring requirements have been identified and recommendations for next steps have been included in the handbook. The handbook is a comprehensive document aimed at supporting not only the existing oPEN Living Labs but also newcomers to the project, as well as other projects working on PENs and energy retrofit projects in Europe and beyond.

To support the oPEN Living Labs in the adoption of Living Lab methodologies, tools and methods within the operations of their Living Labs, a needs-oriented mentoring framework was implemented by ENoLL and HES-SO, including activities of diverse formats, from bilateral meetings to open to everyone sessions for knowledge exchange.

¹ <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/resources-and-tools/articles/renovation-strategy-tool-achieve-net-zero-neighbourhood>

² <https://www.hevs.ch/en/projects/energy-living-lab-8908>

³ <https://enoll.org/>

⁴ https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/D1-4_Capacity-Building-Handbook-Mentoring-report-89.pdf

Figure 5 oPEN Living Labs mentoring framework, ENoLL & HES-SO

The mentoring sessions are organised with each oPEN Living Lab individually every two months. The agenda of these sessions is demand-driven, steered by the specific and current needs of the oPEN Living Labs. Next to this, reflective monitoring¹ is part of these sessions. To support the reflective monitoring process, ENoLL developed a panel matrix to keep track of the stakeholders' participation in each of these activities organised by the Living Labs. Based on the identified needs and outcomes of the bilateral sessions, mentoring webinars are organised by ENoLL and HES-SO every 3-4 months. These webinars aim to encourage experience sharing and collaboration on current relevant topics and are open to everyone interested within the oPEN Lab consortium.

The knowledge exchange meetings are organised with all three oPEN Living Labs every six months to foster cross-fertilization between the Labs. ENoLL sessions are open online sessions organised by ENoLL (beyond the oPEN Lab project) to offer the possibility to oPEN Living Labs to exchange experiences with ENoLL members and external stakeholders.

Finally, the work package (WP) meetings aim to close the loops between all other parts of the mentoring framework by reflecting on the outcomes of the bilateral mentoring sessions and knowledge webinars. This allows to safeguard the progress of the oPEN Living Labs from the task and deliverable perspective.

4. Best Living Lab practices

The implementation of a Positive Energy Neighbourhood (PEN) as a Living Lab implies a great challenge. Therefore, it is important to design a strategy to raise public awareness and actively engage the different actors and stakeholders. Disseminating information, providing recommendations and designing appropriate tools for the different types of stakeholders is crucial to create an approach that engages and includes not only citizens, but also the public government and private sector. Within the oPEN Lab project multiple best practices for stakeholder engagement and awareness raising² have been developed by project partners across the three oPEN Living Labs.

Crowd Mapping Tool (Living Lab Pamplona)

This crowd mapping tool³ developed within the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona is a website application that enables citizen interaction by letting them give their opinion on different topics like energy, comfort, mobility, etc⁴. The data is geo-referenced and contributes to the generation of a collective map of the neighbourhood that shows how people live and use the environment in terms of energy consumption and mobility

¹ <https://coda.io/@vito/nexuslearn/reflexive-monitoring-150>

² https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/H2020_oPEN-Lab_D2.3_Best-Practices-for-Citizen-Engagement-and-Awareness-Raising-to-Facilitate-PEN-Transition-watermark.pdf

³ <https://rochapealivinglab.com/>

⁴ <https://openlab-project.eu/toolbox/crowd-mapping/>

patterns. This data is used as a basis for identifying potential areas of improvement within the neighbourhood.

Figure 6 Illustration of the Crowd mapping tool oPEN Living Lab Pamplona

Renovation as a service (Living Lab Tartu)

To promote renovation in Soviet-era buildings and among Apartment Owner Associations (AOAs), the Tartu City in collaboration with the Tartu Regional Energy Agency (TREA) developed a Renovation as a Service (RaaS)¹ concept. This approach helps managers of AOAs to overcome obstacles involved in renovations. The service was activated in January 2023 and will operate until the end of 2026.

The aim of the service is to help AOAs compete for national renovation financing and to provide technical and financial support to managers of AOAs in the process of preparing renovations and during the construction process. The RaaS vision of the City of Tartu consists of eight components:

1. Collection of consumption data.
2. Calculation of new energy labels.
3. A review of the structural and technical state of the apartment building.
4. Provision of a renovation plan based on the technical state of the building and national renovation standards.
5. Estimation of the renovation costs and home costs post-renovation.
6. Assistance in applying for national financing.
7. Assistance in tenders for the design.
8. Assistance in tenders for the construction.

¹ <https://tarturenoveerib.ee/en/activities/>

Community-based art works (Living Lab Genk)

The artwork “*Now or Never*” in Waterschei brings together art, sustainability, and technology in a project shaped by the local community. Developed as part of the oPEN Lab initiative, the project invited residents to take part in four interactive workshops where they created collages that were later printed on solar panels. In September 2024, Waterschei saw the inauguration of its first participatory public artwork, featuring “*Now or Never*”, an installation made up of 100 images that reflect the district’s past, present, and future, as well as the broader story of Genk.

The solar panel wall not only acknowledges the area's history and identity but also uses IoT (Internet of Things) technology to improve energy generation and monitor environmental performance in real-time. By supplying clean energy to the community, “*Now or Never*” stands at the intersection of art, technology, and sustainability, highlighting environmental awareness and the power of collective effort.

Figure 7 Collaborative artwork "Now or Never" in the oPEN Living Lab Genk

Collaborative mural (Living Lab Pamplona)

In the Rochapea neighborhood, the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona has co-created a collaborative mural as a powerful reflection on climate change and the pivotal role of women in shaping a sustainable future. Situated on the wall of Colegio La Compasión Escolapios, this mural is the first of four artworks focused on energy issues and aimed at enhancing urban spaces, fostering community connections, and raising awareness about sustainability. Created through a series of workshops between March and June 2024, the

project involved residents and local actors in every stage — from co-designing the narrative to collectively painting the mural. Guided by local artists the mural tells the story of Rochapea’s evolution: from its pre-industrial past, where women were central to sustaining community life, through urban industrialization, to a greener future marked by inclusivity, diversity, and energy efficiency. The mural’s imagery, tied together by the flowing Arga River and symbolic birds, celebrates Rochapea’s heritage while envisioning its sustainable transformation.

The collaborative mural makes abstract concepts of sustainability tangible, inspires dialogue, and visualizes a shared vision for a more inclusive and energy-conscious neighborhood. By integrating art, technology, and participation, the project bridges creative expression with actionable change, making it a cornerstone of Rochapea’s Living Lab activities.

The inclusive process of co-creation strengthened neighborhood connections and fostered a renewed sense of ownership and cultural identity. Through the combined efforts of the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona and local residents, the mural not only revitalizes public space but also inspires ongoing innovation and unity within the community.

Figure 8 Collaborative mural on the wall of Colegio La Compasión Escolapios in the oPEN Living Lab Pamplona

oPEN Lab Toolbox

The oPEN Lab toolbox¹ brings together the best practices collected through the project in relation to Positive Energy Neighbourhoods. It is a repository of the most relevant and innovative methods and tools developed and used within the oPEN Lab project to provide policy makers and industry representatives with insights and knowledge and to help them select most appropriate approaches for their actions. Tools can be filtered by phase or by topic. Therefore, it also includes best practices concerning public participation & communication, capacity building & governance, design thinking, but also business models & finance, policy, and technology & renovation.

Figure 9 Screenshot of the oPEN Lab toolbox

Open call for innovators

To open up the oPEN Living Labs to external innovators, an open call² is activated for the whole duration of the project. This initiative allows external innovators to co-create and co-design innovative solutions with inhabitants from the three oPEN Living Labs in a real-life environment. The open call is open for SMEs, start-ups, and large enterprises, but also research institutions, governments and associations representing citizens. After submission of their innovation the innovators are put in contact directly with oPEN Living Labs. The call is kept as simple as possible to attract all kinds of innovators, not only focused on technical solutions, but also proposing social innovations.

¹ <https://openlab-project.eu/toolbox/>

² <https://openlab-project.eu/open-call/>

Figure 10 Screenshot of the oPEN Lab open call

5. Living Lab challenges

Regulatory barriers

Although Positive Energy Neighbourhoods (PENs) offer multiple benefits for the community and society, such as improved comfort and public health, social inclusion, climate resilience and value retention, currently PEN projects rely heavily on public funding and policy support. Structured guidance is needed to facilitate further uptake of PENs. In light of this, several regulatory barriers have emerged, including those related to energy performance, demand-side flexibility, and the collective production, sharing, and selling of energy.

All oPEN Living Labs aim to improve energy performances and bring their pilot buildings to Nearly-zero energy and zero-emission building (NZEB) standards¹, but none of the countries involved in the oPEN Lab project has put in place incentives to trigger conditions for achieving these standards via positive energy buildings and PENs. Next to this, long permitting processes and strict technical requirements for installation of renewable energy sources create difficulties for PEN planning and investments. Also, low flexibility of urban planning regulations slows down innovative solutions for energy performance improvement. For instance, in the oPEN Living Lab Genk an energy box is placed outside the houses, but the current regulatory framework is not yet adapted to this innovative approach. Therefore, a regulatory sandbox from urban planning regulations was needed to permit their installation.

For PENs to unfold their full potential a regulatory framework enabling collective energy production, storage and shoring is needed. However, in the three different countries of the oPEN Lab project, different understandings of the concepts related to PENs like Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Collective Energy Communities (CECs) appear, resulting in different levels of implementation. For instance, tariff and contracting structures in Estonia don't provide a system to share energy virtually, even within one apartment building, since every apartment owner has their own contract with

¹ Ohene, E., Chan, A. P., & Darko, A. (2022). Review of global research advances towards net-zero emissions buildings. *Energy and buildings*, 266, 112142.

an energy provider, but RECs and CECs would need separate meters and changes to all the individual contracts.

Moreover, the Electricity Market Act in Estonia charges transfer fees (costs associated with moving electricity from one place to another) from batteries for small consumers. This act, blocking demand-side flexibility, needs to be adapted to remove these costs and avoid double taxation to stimulate energy sharing and storage by making it more financially viable for small consumers.

In an attempt to provide insights for policy makers, but also the financial market, policy recommendations¹ and policy roadmaps² were developed within the oPEN Lab, together with recommendations to overcome the financial and market barriers³.

Renovation costs

When Russia started the war in Ukraine, it affected multiple fields including the construction and energy sectors. As a result, energy prices raised to unprecedented levels, stimulating governments to subsidize energy costs. This approach weakened the business case for implementing PENs by reducing the economic incentive for long-term energy efficiency investments. Such dynamics created significant obstacles within the oPEN Lab project since many residents prioritized other needs over investments in energy solutions offered by the oPEN Lab project due to social uncertainty and economic insecurity. Despite this the oPEN Living Labs in Genk and Pamplona managed to deeply renovate buildings, but in Tartu they needed to change the project approach completely, even moving to a different area in the city which of course causes an extensive delay.

Communication and stress handling

Due to the complexity and timing of the deep renovations within the three oPEN Living Labs, challenges in communicating with residents have arisen. Uncertainty about the financial impact and renovation timelines has also caused tension in some Living Lab areas.

In Genk (Flanders) the renovation works were paused to adjust the misaligned expectations between all involved stakeholders, resulting in a renewed renovation approach. The lessons learned from these tensions include aligned expectation management for residents and constructors throughout the whole process, providing all stakeholders with a lean comprehensive planning, upfront visibility about the renovations for residents, more clearly defined responsibilities of involved stakeholders and actively engaging citizens as actors of changes.

¹ <https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/OpenLab-Positive-Energy-Neighbourhood-2.pdf>

² https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/D7.1-EU-level-Policy-roadmap-outline-FINAL_Draft.pdf

³ https://openlab-project.eu/app/uploads/OpenLab-Positive-Energy-Neighbourhoods-Overcoming-financial-and-market-barriers_FINAL.pdf

The Tartu oPEN Living Lab focuses on large apartment buildings with high population. Therefore, it's hard to know if every resident receives all communication and information about the project. Next to this the Living Lab faces a group of residents which are sceptical of the renovations, trying to convince other residents to question proposed solutions. However, the Living Lab team tries to make sure these sceptical residents are also heard by trying to explain the details of the renovations and understanding their concerns behind the construction price.

Finally, in Pamplona, the big size of the project created a risk of over-information for local stakeholders beyond their interest. In some cases, this led to disinformation through uncontrolled channels possibly undermining the project. Therefore, they focused on getting trusted local agents to understand the project well and involve these agents in explaining the process to the rest of the local stakeholders. Next to this, a PEN office was installed in the neighbourhood where all local stakeholders could receive clear information about the project and where questions are answered, and opinions are heard.

6. Next steps

The oPEN Lab project will continue until 2026 and in the remaining period of the project ENoLL and HES-SO will further support and mentor the three oPEN Living Labs focusing on long-term active user involvement and engagement and the orchestration of multi-stakeholder participation in Living Labs. Bilateral mentoring sessions to tap into actual needs of each individual oPEN Living Lab will offer the possibility to all oPEN Living Labs to call upon the Living Lab experience of ENoLL. Next to this they will also help to identify possible topics for further mentoring webinars for all oPEN Living Labs. Moreover, further exchange meetings between all three Living Labs will be organized to allow them to learn from each other. Finally, in the spring of 2025 another ENoLL session will be organised to offer the possibility to oPEN Living Labs to exchange experiences with ENoLL members and external stakeholders.

Towards the end of the project, in the second semester of 2025, the three oPEN Living Labs will be benchmarked based on the harmonized evaluation framework for Living Labs¹ developed by ENoLL to provide them with a tailored feedback report including recommendations for further growth towards becoming a stable Living Lab beyond the scope of the oPEN Lab project. This evaluation process will look at six essential building blocks of a stable Living Lab: strategy, operations, openness, users & reality, value & impact, and stability & scale-up.

Finally, all co-creation practices will be collected and integrated into the updated final version of the capacity building handbook of oPEN Lab to support other energy transition projects.

¹ Vervoort, K., Konstantinidis, E., Santonen, T., Petsani, D., Servais, D., De Boer, D., Spagnoli, F., Onur, O., Bertolin, J., Trousse, B., Desole, M., & Bamidis, P. (2025, januari 10). Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14626124>

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